

A facile method for preparation of aromatic isocyanates using bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate

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A facile synthesis of aromatic isocyanates using bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate (BTC) is reported with high yields of products. BTC is used to supply phosgene *in situ* in stoichiometric amounts.

Aromatic isocyanates are versatile intermediates in the synthesis of important classes of organic compounds. The most widely used method for the synthesis of isocyanates is the reaction of amines with phosgene¹. Phosgene is a highly toxic gas. Liquid trichloromethyl chloroformate² (used as a phosgene substitute) has been proved to be useful in the synthesis of isocyanates³, but its transport and storage pose considerable problems. Bis(trichloromethyl)carbonate (BTC) was reported as a safe replacement for phosgene and trichloromethyl chloroformate⁴. BTC is a crystalline, stable solid (m.p. 80°, b.p. 206°; at the boiling point, only slight decomposition to phosgene occurs⁵). Under the influence of a nucleophile, 1 mol of BTC reacts similarly to 3 mol of phosgene⁴. On the other hand, BTC has the advantage of being much easier and safer to handle than the highly toxic gaseous phosgene and the liquid trichloromethyl chloroformate.

Results and Discussion

Aromatic isocyanates (**2**) have been prepared from arylamines (**1**) using BTC.

The results (Table 1) shows that the nature of substituents in the aromatic ring affects the yields of products. If the substituents are electron-withdrawing groups, excess BTC is needed to complete the reaction. Arylamine was reacted with BTC as a nucleophile. The electron-withdrawing groups decreased the nucleophilicity of the arylamine, causing the decreased of product yield. The possible mechanism is presented in Scheme 1.

BTC undergoes nucleophilic attack at the carbonyl carbon by arylamine to form one molecule of intermediate **3** and one molecule of trichloromethanol. Then **3** decomposes to one molecule of intermediate **4** and one molecule of phosgene, and trichloromethanol decomposes to another molecule of phosgene and one molecule of HCl. Each molecule of phosgene generated reacts immediately with another molecule of arylamine **1** to form one molecule of intermediate **4** and one molecule of HCl. During heating, intermediate **4** is dissociated to one molecule of HCl and one molecule of the product. Hence, each molecule of BTC can produce three molecules of the product. However, the exact mechanism is yet to be clarified and a more detailed study is in progress in our laboratory.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Preparation of aromatic isocyanates (2a-h)

Compd. no.	R	Mole ratio (Arylamine : BTC)	Yield (%)*	Purity (%)**
2a	4-isopropyl	1 : 0.37	98.2	98.5
b	2-isopropyl	1 : 0.37	92.4	94.1
c	4-chloro	1 : 0.5	89.4	98.7
d	3-chloro	1 : 0.5	91.0	99.1
e	2-chloro	1 : 0.5	90.3	93.6
f	3-trifluoromethyl	1 : 0.5	87.6	95.5
g	3,4-dichloro	1 : 0.5	91.9	97.9
h	3-chloro-4-methyl	1 : 0.5	93.2	96.7

*Isolated yields based on arylamines. **Determined by GLC.

In comparison with phosgene and trichloromethyl chloroformate, BTC, being a solid, is safe and convenient to handle. A further advantage is that, only equivalent amount or moderate excess of BTC (mole ratio to arylamine 0.34~0.5 : 1.0) is needed to complete the phosgenation reaction, which means that only small quantity of hazardous phosgene gas will be emitted or none at all. Phosgene, however, has to be used in several folds excess in the phosgenation reaction with arylamines⁷. Additionally, BTC is quite stable under normal conditions, so that the transportation and storage is easy.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. GLC analyses were carried out using a glass column (1 m × 3 mm i.d.) packed with 7% SE-30/Gas chrom Q of 180–250 μm. Purity of all the compounds was determined by GLC. IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker VECTOR 22 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC-80 instrument with tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

General procedure : To a stirred solution of BTC (1.1 g, 3.7 mmol) dissolved in dichloroethane (10 ml) and heated to 70° was added a solution of arylamine (**1**; 10 mmol) in dichloroethane (10 ml) dropwise over a period of 30 min. The mixture was then heated to 83° and slightly refluxed. After the solid diminished (about 1–2 h), the solvent along with the generated HCl and the unreacted phosgene were vaporized at normal pressure and then the residue was distilled under vacuum to give an aromatic isocyanates (**2a-h**) : **2a**, colorless oil, b.p. 114–116°/3 kPa (lit.⁸ 85°/4 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2963, 2270, 1608, 1577; 1528, 833 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.17–1.26 (6H, d, CH₃), 2.87 (1H, m, CH), 6.91–7.21 (4H, m, ArH); **b**, colorless oil, b.p. 95–98°/3 kPa (lit.⁹ b.p. 66–67°/5 mmHg), ν_{\max} 2965, 2269, 1601, 1578, 1507, 1070, 754 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.17–1.26 (6H, d, CH₃), 3.20 (1H, m, CH), 7.04–7.25 (4H, m, ArH); **c**, white crystals, m.p. 30–32°, b.p. 108–110°/4 kPa (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 31–32°, b.p. 80.6–80.9°/9.5 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2267, 1597, 1511, 1108, 827 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 6.96–7.34 (4H, m, ArH); **d**, colorless oil, b.p. 105–107°/3 kPa (lit.¹⁰ 83–86°/10.5 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2263, 1596, 1577, 1502, 778, 676

cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 6.96–7.43 (4H, m, ArH); **e**, colorless oil, b.p. 98–100°/3 kPa, (lit.¹⁰ 83.5°/10 mmHg), ν_{\max} 2264, 1597, 1502, 778, 676 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 7.00–7.27 (4H, m, ArH); **f**, colorless oil, b.p. 76–78°/3 kPa (lit.¹¹ 54°/11 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2274, 1617, 1595, 1514, 1324, 1131, 797, 696 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 7.25–7.41 (4H, m, ArH); **g**, white crystal, m.p. 41–42°, b.p. 120–123°/3 kPa (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 45°, b.p. 111–112°/12 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2267, 1595, 1563, 1499, 816, 576 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 6.91–7.27 (3H, m, ArH); **h**, colorless oil, b.p. 120–124°/5 kPa (lit.¹² 107°/3 mm Hg), ν_{\max} 2269, 1609, 1567, 1515, 816, 577 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 2.33 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.91–7.25 (3H, m, ArH).

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